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D4.6 – Ontology ecosystem reference implementation

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
API	Application Programming Interface
RDF	Resource Description Framework
OWL	Web Ontology Language

Keywords

Ontology development; System, Software, Knowledge Graph Generation

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Executive Summary

This document describes the OntoCommons proposal for the ontology ecosystem reference implementation as one of the results of the project tasks T4.1 “Stakeholders gathering and Focused workshops”, T4.2 “Scoping and structuring of the ecosystem” and T4.5 “Reference implementation tooling”. The results presented in this document is not limited to one pipeline of systems and tools to be used as baseline for ontology developments, instead, a number of tools are aligned with main ontology development activities and data annotation processes in order to offer a wider range of configurations. This deliverable also reports on the second Focused Workshop organized by WP4 entitled “Ontology Engineering and Knowledge Graphs (OE&KG) tool ecosystem” held the 31st of August 2022.

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1. Introduction

On the one hand, OntoCommons WP4 aims to provide recommendations on the principles, best practices and methods for the development and maintenance of ontology. In that context, deliverable D4.2 [Fernández-Izquierdo et al., 2021] presented the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology, the methodological framework for the development and documentation of ontologies, including not only the activities that should be performed in the ontology development process, but also the guidelines, resources, and recommendations to support it. On the other hand, WP4 aims at proposing a reference implementation tooling for ontology development and data annotation, which is described in this document.

In addition, during the process of defining this reference implementation other resources have been taken as inputs as the OntoCommons “D4.1. Ontology ecosystem specification” [d’ Aquin et al., 2021], “D4.2 Methodological framework for ontology management” [Fernández-Izquierdo et al., 2021], “D4.3. Landscape Analysis of Ontology Engineering Tools” [Skjæveland et al., 2021] and “D5.1 Requirements on ontology tools and ontologies and criteria for selection of further cases” as well as the results of the 2 focuses workshops organized by this WP as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overview of resources and events related to D4.6

2. Methodology

This section is devoted to the description of the workflow followed to create the tools ecosystem. As it can be observed in Figure 2 the following steps were carried out:

- **Step 1: Tools review**
 - **Input:** “D4.3. Landscape Analysis of Ontology Engineering Tools” and expert knowledge in ontology development.
 - **Process:** During this step the list of tools in D4.3 was reviewed and extended with partners knowledge about tools used in ontology development and data annotation.
 - **Output:** Initial tools list.
- **Step 2: Initial tool alignment with methodology**
 - **Input:** “D4.1. Ontology ecosystem specification”, “D4.2 Methodological framework for ontology management” and “D4.3. Landscape Analysis of Ontology Engineering Tools”
 - **Process:** During this step the preliminary classification of systems to be used in the different ontology development activities was taken as input from D4.1 as was extended considering more specific activities detailed in the ontology development methodology described in D4.2. After that, the tools included in the landscape analysis (D4.3) as well as the extended list (step 1) and the tools mentioned in D4.1 were mapped to the specific activities in the methodology.
 - **Output:** Initial mapping between the extended list of tools and methodology activities.
- **Step 3: Workshop organization**
 - **Input:** --
 - **Process:** This step centred around the organization of the 2nd WP4 focused workshop, focusing on the use of ontology development systems in industry. One of the steps for preparing the workshop consisted in defining a short survey to picture the community interest about ontology development and knowledge graph generation tools. Details about the workshop organization and results are further described in Section 3.
 - **Output:** OntoCommons community interest about tools for ontology development and knowledge graphs generation and list of tools presented and used by speakers and attendees.
- **Step 4: Workshop post-processing**
 - **Input:** Initial mapping between the extended list of tools and methodology activities, OC community interest survey results and tools and practices mentioned by the workshop attendees.
 - **Process:** During this process the mapping between extended list of tools and methodology activities were reviewed considering the experiences shared during the workshop and the OC community respondents to the survey carried out before the workshop.
 - **Output:** Updated mapping between extended list of tools and methodology activities
- **Step 5: Partners consultation**
 - **Input:** Initial mapping between extended list of tools and methodology activities.
 - **Process:** OntoCommons partners were asked to provide feedback about the mappings between the tools and methodology activities.
 - **Output:** Updated mapping between extended list of tools and methodology activities.

Figure 2. OntoCommons reference tooling generation workflow

3. 2nd Focused Workshop

The 2nd focused workshop organized by WP4 about ontology engineering in practice entitled “Ontology Engineering and Knowledge Graphs (OE&KG) tool ecosystem” was held online the 31st of August of 2022. The workshop included 11 talks about ontology engineering and knowledge graph generation tools and methodologies.

In order to define the workshop topics and format a short survey was launch through the OntoCommons mailing list and social media channels. The questions of the survey are listed in Annex 1. There were 101 responses to the survey.

According to the answer the preferred option for the format and date was online and the 31st of August as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. Even though the preference for organizers would have been fully in person or hybrid it was decided to ask the potential audience due to the raising cases of COVID during the summer and the fact that the workshop was planned during the summer vacation in Europe according to DoA and couldn't be postponed much to meet the project planification of deliverables. Finally, there were 115 registrations for the workshop having a peak of 95 attendees.

Figure 3. Workshop preferred format

If you were attending the workshop, which dates would you attend?

87 respuestas

Figure 4. Workshop preferred date

In order to draft the workshop agenda and invite relevant speakers the answers to the questions “Please list functions and features that you think are missing from those tools, or that are not sufficiently supported by those tools in your experience.” and “Please list tools that you hear off and you would like to have more information about so that you can incorporate them in your processes.” were analyzed. In the following, main answers to these questions are listed after filtering answers of the type “NA” or “I don’t know”.

- *Please list functions and features that you think are missing from those tools, or that are not sufficiently supported by those tools in your experience (taken literally):*
 - *Ontology versioning*
 - *Ontology change management*
 - *Ontology/language-specific object binding*
 - *CI/CD for ontologies integration and deployment*
 - *Existing vocabulary discovery*
 - *Ontology extension/dependency management*
 - *Ontology reuse, data validation*
 - *Reasoning rules results*
 - *Major integration with python dev.*
 - *modularisation, reasoning performance, combination of DL reasoning and generative rules*
 - *Ontology integration*
 - *Easy end user GUIs*
 - *Visualisation of ontologies is very rudimentar and not easy to use to make several views of the ontologies*
 - *Collaborative editing an ontology.*
 - *Logical validation*
 - *Mapping of second order logic, 3/4 dimensional models*
 - *Terminology Service (Versioning),*
 - *WebProtege (Git integration)*
 - *Ontology development validation (e.g. according to OWL rules)*

- *graphic ontology development*
- *Mapping Data to Terms*
- *Need tools to map terms across ontologies and correct ontologies*
- *Need tools for linked terms as these are the main gaps - e.g., bio-nano interactions, protein corona, etc.*
- *Visualization of universals and particulars in one graph, as it is hard to explain graphs to people not involved in semantic technologies. A graph 'browser' would be amazing.*
- *Sensitivity*
- *Surveying ontologies to reuse/align with, ontology visualisation, connecting the ontology to use with software*
- *Curation tools. Manual mapping workflows (e.g. reviewing autogenerated mappings); quick table based ontology-aware data curation (ala <https://github.com/cidgoh/DataHarmonizer>), web-based editing tools for curating ontologies such as the ones developed by <https://github.com/ontodev> team.*
- *Better tutorials on how to get going that do not immediately through you into a specific tech stack.*
- *There is a ton of resources needed to support the process, but my sense is that the biggest issue is the Gap between manual curation and automated curation - two few tools allow seamless interplay between the two, which leads to costly transformation pipelines that translate output from KG machine learning, ontology matching etc into ontology axioms and KG relations. We are not nearly ready to take the human out of the loop for serious multimodal KG building.*
- *Tools that bridge the gap between KG learning (pytorch geometric, any graph neural networks etc) and knowledge graph curation.*
- *workflows and concepts for OE that abstracts the OE part (for practitioners in a domain or horizontal flow)*
- *Steep learning curve, difficult to use.*
- *Easy integration of external ontology modules (module extraction, SLME vs MIREOT), easy reuse of existing desing patterns and ontology mappings (OBO vs. w3c), shape generation for data validation, ontology based/mapped data schemas (LinkML, ISA-Tools, SSSOM, ?)*
- *Reuse of modelling patterns, generation of complex expressions based on tabular data, handling of blank nodes, generation of multiple ontologies based on the same tabular data set.*
- *Ontology edition from natural language, ontology alignment, ontology of business objects*
- *A unified environment for modeling both classes and instances*
- *reification of triples could be better supported; algebraic provenance characterization; knowledge graph transformation systems; tools & mechanisms for pragmatic interoperability*
- *Identification, Reuse, Modularisation*
- *Sometimes Protege may seem difficult when you want to make changes in the hierarchy of the ontology, or reasoners may not give enough insights on the errors*
- *Explanation of inconsistencies*
- *There are a number of aspects OLS can deal with better. We are working with experts and users to better understand their needs. Some known needs are: 1. Need for multi-language*

- support - recently added 2. Bulk queries with filtering options 3. Annotations on annotations, i.e., provenance information*
- *validation, reference checks*
 - *Natural Language Processing and SPARQL and RDF Query visualization*
 - *graphic representation and manipulation*
 - *RDF star, collections, scalability, distribution*
 - *easy visualization*
 - *Tools for smooth transition from drafting to implementation; tools for easy and multiple instantiation; efficient graphical editors; visualization tools*
 - *SHACL editor, SHACL generation from OWL, integration of python library rdflib with pandas and R2RML/ontop mapping language for doing ETL in python*
 - *Lack of "expressiveness", unnecessary complexity, lack of clarity etc.*
 - *most are very difficult to use for non-experts, still*
 - *Graph query*
 - *Sharing, standardization, and mentoring*
 - *Intuitive user interface. Automatic verification*
 - *Ability to select ontologies and metadata already widely used and automated suggestions based on W3C and Schema.org standards.*
 - *Convenient visualisation*
 - *Repos for BLOB-data that can be easily linked to KGs*
 - *Numerous. Few tools support an integrated and design-rich experience.*
 - *reasoning/inference*
 - *Versioning, ontology change management*
 - *reasoning*
 - *Graph representation*
 - *scope and configuration management*
 - *Ontology standard queries, reasoning, facilitate ontology matching*
 - *Ontology testing/validation/quality assessment*
 - *Templating and validation for ontology building*
 - *reasoning, cause-and effect explainability*
 - *Better visualization and browsing; better integration of multiple ontologies*
 - *Visualisation is still poorly covered, esp for ontology axioms (beyond simple graphs). Support for working with many modules is quite weak, would help to have that. Lack of quality assurance tools/methods/rulesets.*
 - *A feature for easily sharing ontology files, similar to Github, with a search using a filter for finding related ontology in order not to create already developed ones.*
 - *property handling mechanism*
 - *Support of Protegé and app to xls o csv DB*
 - *For ontology drafting/editing, I wish that tools could support a collaborative mode (similar to Google Docs, for instance)*
 - *Smart support for entity reuse*
 - *Powerpoint is clumsy to arrange things*

- *Diagram from ontology code (other than WebOWL, which only includes name of the class and object properties), Ontology documentation with support for big ontologies (Widoco has no pagination functionality and this hinders the generation of doc for big ontologies)*
- *Please list tools that you hear off and you would like to have more information about so that you can incorporate them in your processes (taken literally):*
 - *Shacl*
 - *Ruben Taelman's rdf-objects is a binding library I want to look into at some point*
 - *Would like to learn more about any(great if open source) tool about ontology engineering management , and maybe some advance features on protege and how to manage/manipulate ontologies using programming libraries(python n stuff)-Thanks*
 - *Haystack, BrickSchema, Real Estate Core, ifcOWL*
 - *Themis ontology evaluation*
 - *Integration with Graph DBMS such as GraphDB and Fluree for example*
 - *Archimate*
 - *Protege*
 - *Neo4j, scibite etc*
 - *RDFox*
 - *Knowledge Graph systems*
 - *PoolParty*
 - *Cinchy*
 - *I look for tools to automate translation of dataset in knowledge graphs*
 - *Graffoo, Top Braid Composer, tools on data preparation and generation.*
 - *SolidProject, LDP, GraphQL-LD*
 - *Owl*
 - *StarDog*
 - *Ontocommons*
 - *Protégé*
 - *XML/JSON to OWL and XML, JSON to RDFSTAR*
 - *Morph-KGC*
 - *rdflib, owl*
 - *Logical reasoners*
 - *Quality assesement*
 - *Chowlk*
 - *OntoBrowser*
 - *OBDA tools, API generation tools, ontology quality assurance tools*
 - *All KG learning approaches (KG embeddings, GNNs, etc) are black boxes a lot of the time and hard to integrate into many of the KG pipelines.*
 - *I'm looking to evaluate and potentially incorporate comunica.js. But in general I need ideas and inspiring examples of online implementations*
 - *ODK, ROBOT, LinkML, OAK, RDFlib*
 - *OTTR*
 - *SparkCognition, Conexus*
 - *any of the tools actually/allegedly developed by ontocommons*
 - *OntoBee, OntoText*

- *RDFOx*
- *General practical information about implementation steps (software to use, steps needed, etc.) in form of a tutorial or something similar is currently missing*
- *REST API Spec generation from SHACL, SHACL editors*
- *protege*
- *Apache Tinkerpop, Pool Party*
- *collaborative ontology development and interlinking*
- *Text mining to extract domain terminology. Automatic categorization, to discover if a concept is an object, an actor, a process, or an attribute*
- *Virtuoso*
- *Cameo*
- *More graphical tools for ontology design.*
- *Karma Data Integration, Ontofox*
- *UML generation from OWL*
- *Fuseki, to add access to the Ontopanel*
- *SPARQL*
- *SHACL*
- *I would like to present OPCloud online. I will be at MIT so time-wise it can be tricky.*
- *Synaptica, WebVOWL*
- *Would like to know more about existing ontology repositories.*
- *Protégé-OWL Plug-in for importing spreadsheet content into OWL ontologies*
- *Tools supporting the LOT methodology (esp. their concertation)*
- *Something for visualization*
- *EMMOntoPy, CASPAR*

In addition, there was a question in the survey for respondents to propose talks about their tools or experience. The topic proposed by potential speakers were (taken literally):

- *I think vocabulary discovery and extension is a topic which is really hurting adoption by a wider developers community*
- *Semantic cartography of enterprises*
- *Human Services Ontologies*
- *Ontology authoring/editing, ontologies to reuse, ontology modularisation, tools*
- *Model Based Systems Engineering (Design to Manufacturing)*
- *A presentation: Ontology-Driven Data Access and Data Integration with An Application in the Materials Design Domain*
- *Building Digital Twin Models*
- *Ontology management and creation*
- *integrating ontologies into bench researchers activities*
- *At the panel, I will find a place to discuss my special innovative ideas, so it will be more effective than this presentation.*
- *Use cases from built environment / urban planning where powerful visualisation is needed (for example 3D models) as part of contextual understanding*
- *Ontologies for industrial engineering : Objectives, methods and tools.*

- *High level overview of the new ICICLE.ai institute, where we see ontology/kg fitting in, the importance of specific reusable ontology toolchain infrastructure features, and integration of new ai tools, like conversations agents, into the toolchain*
- *domain-to-top level and complex (heteromorphic) alignment; provenance/grounding/epistemic metadata; mid-level ontology*
- *Abridging knowledge extraction, ontology design, and reuse*
- *"1. Ontology Lookup Service and how it is used at EBI. 2. Vocabularies vs Ontologies - When to use a reasoner"*
- *The Intersection between Materials Science Engineering and Semantic Web*
- *High throughput KGs for edge computing in industrial usecase*
- *The proposed dates don't suit me.*
- *Methodology and workflow presentations*
- *ontology adaption in various domains (life science, agri-food...)*
- *Role of ontologies in the joint cognitive work of formulating analytical models (e.g. for manufacturing applications)*
- *An agile ontology engineering methodology: from informal to formal*
- *Knowledge Reconciliation through uncertain sources (methods and challenges)*
- *graph based (neo4j) development of Schema and Applications*
- *Ontology development process for a project and Comparison by using two ontology languages.*
- *SciBite experiences in developing ontology authoring tools and KGs for Pharma industry*
- *OPM ISO 19450 and its minimal ontology implementation in the OPCloud tool.*
- *Real-world applications of ontologies. How to manage versioning. How should ontologies be shared between researchers, standardization bodies and industry.*
- *ontology for psychometric scales*
- *Manufacturing*
- *Ontology drafting*
- *Methodology and tools for ontology development in BASF*

After analyzing the answers from the 3 questions listed above some developers/maintainers from the tools mentioned were invited to participate in the workshop as well as some of the respondents proposing topics. In addition, the OntoCommons teams also looked for potential speakers from industry experienced in the whole lifecycle of ontologies and knowledge graphs. Finally, the event agenda accommodated the following 11 talks¹:

- **11:15 - 12:15 Ontology development tools - Part 1**
 - *Validating ontologies through requirements with Themis* (Alba Fernández-Izquierdo - BASF)
 - *Ontology drafting in PURO* (Vojtěch Svátek / Marek Dudáš - Prague University of Economics and Business)
- **12:30 - 13:30 Ontology development tools - Part 2**
 - *Reasonable Ontology Templates (OTTR)* (Martin Georg Skjæveland - University of Oslo)
 - *Democratisation of Enterprise Knowledge Graphs (EKG)* (Katariina Kari - IKEA)

¹ See full agenda description at <https://www.ontocommons.eu/news-events/events/workshop-ontology-engineering-and-knowledge-graphs-tool-ecosystem>

- 14:45 - 16:15 **Ontology development end-to-end**
 - *Methodology and tools for ontology development in BASF* (Alba Fernández-Izquierdo / Iker Esnaola - BASF)
 - *OLS - The Ontology Lookup Service* (Henriette Harmse - European Bioinformatics Institute | EMBL-EBI)
 - *Building an Enterprise Ontology Management System for the Pharmaceutical Industry* (Simon Jupp - SciBite)
- 16:30 - 17:30 **Ontologies in use: Knowledge graph generation - Part 1**
 - *Declarative Knowledge Graph Construction: A practical introduction* (David Chaves-Fraga - Universidad Politécnica de Madrid - KULeuven)
 - *Applying Ontotext GraphDB and Ontotext Refine for building industrial Knowledge Graphs* (Miroslav Chervenski / Vladimir Alexiev - Ontotext)
- 17:30 - 19:00 **Ontologies in use: Knowledge graph generation - Part 2**
 - *MatVis - A Framework to Visually Represent Material Science Engineering Methods and RDF Knowledge Graph Creation* (Andre Valdestilhas - BAM Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung)
 - *Health application* (Jaan Altosaar - Columbia University)
 - *Open Semantic Lab - Bringing ontologies into everyday science* (Simon Stier - Fraunhofer)

4. Reference implementation

This section presents the ontology ecosystem reference implementation that includes not only the suggested tools for ontology development but also for data semantic annotation, that is to exploit the ontologies generating knowledge graphs. This ecosystem is aligned with the Linked Open Terms methodology presented in D4.2 and extended with basic activities for exploiting ontologies. In order to build this tool ecosystem, the preliminary specification presented in D4.1 has been reviewed and aligned with D4.2 methodology.

It should be noted that not all the sub activities included in the methodology have been taken into account as the systems to carry them out could be considered in a more general level, more precisely this decision was taken for the sub activities in the ontology requirements specification and the ontology maintenance. The result of extending the preliminary specification and the LOT methodology in order to generate the ontology development and exploitation consolidated workflow is presented in Figure 5. From this point, the functional modules identified in D4.1 have been 1) extended, 2) aligned with the ontology development and exploitation consolidated workflow and 3) provided with examples of tools available for such functionality.

The result of this process is shown in Figure 6, in which for each ontology development and exploitation activity is aligned with the services or categories of tools that could be used to assisted such activity. The services or categories of tools are located under each activity in a vertical position, that is, for example, for the “Evaluation” activity one may use systems of the category “Validator”, “Test executor” or “Reasoner”. These functionalities might be useful for more than one activity, for example the category “(Visual) Drafting” tools could be used for the activities included in its “vertical”, that is, they can be used for “Ontology conceptualization”, “Ontology reuse”, “Encoding” and “Evaluation”. It should be noted that one category can appear in more than one place in the figure, for example the category “Repository” that can be used both for looking for ontologies during the “Ontology Reuse” activity and for sharing and promoting the ontology in the “Ontology Publication” activity.

One of the goals of the ecosystem is to lower the learning curve for newcomers to the ontology and knowledge graph development field. In this sense, the tools and systems providing a user-friendly interface are of great value in the ecosystem. However, in order to extend the catalogue of tools included in the ecosystem frameworks and libraries oriented to programming languages have been included under the category “APIs”.

Another particular category is the “Project management, version management and issue tracking” that includes specific systems defined for ontology development life-cycle as well as systems originally designed for supporting the software development community and general purpose systems.

Figure 5. Ontology development and exploitation consolidated workflow generation

Figure 6. Ontology Ecosystem Reference implementation

In the following, each category is briefly described and main pointers for the specific systems included as available tools are provided. It should be noted that the priority for the references are official websites and GitHub repositories in first place or papers when websites and repositories are not available. It should be noted that for some types of tools that are too general there are no particular tools provided in Figure 6, for example for the word cloud systems or tools for processing text. However, some examples are provided from Table 1 to Table 23.

Table 1. Category: Concept extractor

Category	Concept extractor
Description	Concept extractors can be used for processing long texts or a number of requirements in order to rank the most important terms
Related activities	Ontology Requirements Specification
Tool	Reference
Word cloud systems	https://www.wordclouds.com/
Entity recognition	https://huggingface.co/dslim/bert-large-NER

Table 2. Category: Test specification and test executor

Category	Test specification / Test executor
Description	These systems allow generating tests from the ontology requirements to be later used during the ontology evaluation.
Related activities	Ontology requirement specification, Evaluation
Tool	Reference
THEMIS	http://themis.linkeddata.es/
TDD Onto2	https://github.com/kierendavies/tddonto2

Table 3. Category: General docs

Category	General docs
Description	These systems should be used to generate, store and share the project documentation as resources, for example the Ontology Requirement Specification Document, or internal documents as meeting notes or annotations.
Related activities	Ontology Requirements Specification
Tool	Reference
Tables	OpenOffice http://www.openoffice.org/ Google Drive https://www.google.com/drive MS office https://www.office.com/
Docs	OpenOffice http://www.openoffice.org/ Google Drive https://www.google.com/drive MS office https://www.office.com/
Mindmaps	Miro https://miro.com/mind-map/ Mural https://www.mural.co Coggle https://coggle.it/

Table 4. Category: Ontology editor

Category	Ontology editor
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Description	Ontology editors allow for authoring, generating and modify OWL and RDF(S) ontologies. Usually ontology editors include a wide range of plugins or features for ontology authoring related activities including the merge and import of other ontologies. These systems can be also used during the ontology evaluation activity in combination with plug-ins for specific validator or reasoners or just to verify ontology requirements against the model.
Related activities	Ontology conceptualization, Ontology reuse, Encoding, Evaluation
Tool	Reference
Protégé	https://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/ProtegeDesktopUserDocs
WebProtégé	https://protegewiki.stanford.edu/wiki/WebProtege
Fluent Editor	https://www.cognitum.eu/semantics/FluentEditor/
TopBraid Composer	https://archive.topquadrant.com/topbraid-composer-install/
PoolParty	https://www.poolparty.biz/
CAMEO	https://www.3ds.com/products-services/catia/products/no-magic/comeo-systems-modeler/
SousLeSens	https://souslesens.enit.fr

Table 5. Category: (Visual) Drafting

Category	(Visual) Drafting
Description	These systems allow the design of ontological models and the generation of the corresponding code in a visual way oriented to graphical notations. Ontology editors providing GUIs are not considered specific visual drafting tools if no edition following a specific graphical notation is supported.
Related activities	Ontology conceptualization, Ontology reuse, Encoding, Evaluation
Tool	Reference
Chowlk	https://chowlk.linkeddata.es/
crowd-tool	https://crowd-app.fi.uncoma.edu.ar/
Menthor Editor	https://ontouml.org/ontouml/tooling/
OntoPanel	https://github.com/yuechenbam/yuechenbam.github.io
OWBO	https://github.com/mdaquin/OWBO
DiTTO	https://essepuntato.it/ditto/
Gra.fo	https://gra.fo/

Table 6. Category: Ontology Design Pattern Reuse

Category	Ontology Design Pattern Reuse
Description	These tools allow for the reuse of ontology design pattern.
Related activities	Ontology conceptualization, Ontology reuse, Encoding
Tool	Reference
Reasonable Ontology Templates (OTTR)	https://ottr.xyz/
ODP Portal	http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Main_Page

Table 7. Category: Modularizer

Category	Modularizer
Description	These systems aim at generating modules from monolithic ontologies.
Related activities	Ontology reuse, Encoding
Tool	Reference
Ontofox	https://ontofox.hegroup.org/

Table 8. Category: Matcher

Category	Matcher
Description	These systems allow for generating and exploration of ontology alignments.
Related activities	Ontology Reuse, Encoding
Tool	Reference
Alignment Cubes	https://www.ida.liu.se/%7Epatla00/research/AlignmentCubes/

Table 9. Category: Visualizer

Category	Visualizer
Description	These systems aim at providing a user-friendly ontology visualization and navigation. Ontology editors providing GUIs are not considered specific visualizers, however, they can provide plug-ins for more elaborated visualizations. These systems are normally used to analyze existing ontologies that is why the related activity is ontology reuse but they can also be used for ontology documentation.
Related activities	Ontology reuse
Tool	Reference
WebVOWL	http://vowl.visualdataweb.org/webvowl.html

Table 10. Category: Repository

Category	Repository
Description	Ontology repositories allows the registration and/or indexing of ontologies as well as search and look up of ontology terms.
Related activities	Ontology reuse, online publication
Tool	Reference
IndustryPortal	http://industryportal.enit.fr/
LOV	https://lov.linkeddata.es
BARTOC	https://bartoc.org/
Ontohub	https://ontohub.org/
LOV4IoT	https://lov4iot.appspot.com/
BioPortal	https://bioportal.bioontology.org/
OntoBee	https://ontobee.org/
AgroPortal	http://agroportal.lirmm.fr/
ODP Portal	http://ontologydesignpatterns.org/wiki/Main_Page
DBpedia Archivio	https://archivio.dbpedia.org/list
Ontology Lookup Service (OLS)	https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ols/index

Table 11. Category: Validator

Category	Validator
Description	Theses system assist ontology developers to evaluate their ontologies looking for common errors, or by checking constraints.
Related activities	Evaluation
Tool	Reference
OOPS!	https://oops.linkeddata.es/
ASTREA	https://astrea.linkeddata.es/
Shaclgen	https://pypi.org/project/shaclgen/
Shape designer	https://gitlab.inria.fr/jdusart/shexjapp

Table 12. Category: Reasoner

Category	Reasoner
Description	These systems facilitate ontology evaluation activity by looking for potential inconsistencies and incoherencies in the ontologies.
Related activities	Evaluation
Tool	Reference
Pellet	https://github.com/stardog-union/pellet
Fact++,	http://owl.cs.manchester.ac.uk/tools/fact/
Hermit	http://www.hermit-reasoner.com/
Konclude	https://www.derivo.de/en/produkte/konclude.html
ORMiE	https://gitlab.inf.unibz.it/franconi/ormie-release/
Hets	https://github.com/spechub/Hets

Table 13. Category: Documentor

Category	Documentor
Description	These systems facilitate the generation of human-oriented documentation from the OWL ontology code.
Related activities	Documentation
Tool	Reference
WIDOCO	https://dgarijo.github.io/Widoco/doc/tutorial/
LODE	https://essepuntato.it/lode/
pyLODE	https://github.com/RDFLib/pyLODE

Table 14. Category: Publication Server

Category	Publication Server
Description	A publication server can be used to publish the ontology online following content negotiation mechanisms. In this sense a general web server and domain configuration could be set up or systems that facilitate the redirections and provide permanent URIs could be used.
Related activities	Online publication
Tool	Reference
Web servers	General web server to manage web domains.
w3id	https://w3id.org/
purl	https://purl.archive.org/

Table 15. Category: Ontology FAIR validator

Category	Ontology FAIR validator
Description	These systems assess the FAIR level of an ontology or to what extends the FAIR principles are meet.
Related activities	Online publication
Tool	Reference
FOOPS!	https://w3id.org/foops/ (https://foops.linkeddata.es/FAIR_validator.html)
O'FAIRE	https://github.com/agroportal/fairness

Table 16. Category: Issue tracking

Category	Issue tracking
Description	These system allows the reporting of bugs, new requirements or potential enhancements of the ontologies. It should be noted that these systems are also considered for the whole project management but a particular mentioned is done for the ontology maintenance activity.

Related activities	Ontology maintenance
Tool	Reference
GitHub	https://github.com/
GitLab	https://about.gitlab.com/
Jira	https://www.atlassian.com/software/jira
Mantis	https://www.mantisbt.org/

Table 17. Category: Versioning

Category	Versioning
Description	These systems facilitate the creation of versions and dependency handling. Note that other systems could be used for versioning as some of the ones listed in the category “Project management, version management and issue tracking”. For example, the project management systems for general purposes like GitHub, among others, or the ones specific for ontologies like OnToology or VoCol,
Related activities	Ontology maintenance
Tool	Reference
ontology-toolkit	https://github.com/semanticarts/ontology-toolkit

Table 18. Category: Populator

Category	Populator
Description	These systems and specifications allow the generation of RDF data from a different data sources.
Related activities	Data generation
Tool	Reference
LinkML	https://linkml.io/
OpenRefine	https://github.com/OpenRefine/OpenRefine
LODRefine	https://github.com/sparkica/LODRefine
OntoRefine	https://www.ontotext.com/products/ontotext-refine/
R2RML	https://www.w3.org/TR/r2rml/
RML	https://rml.io/specs/rml/
YARRML	https://rml.io/yarrml/
Matey	https://rml.io/yarrml/matey/
Helio	https://oeg-upm.github.io/helio/
Karma	https://usc-isi-i2.github.io/karma/
MORPH	https://morph.oeg.fi.upm.es/
SPARQL-generate	https://ci.mines-stetienne.fr/sparql-generate/
excel2RDF	https://pypi.org/project/excel2rdf/
mimir	https://github.com/mimir-org

Table 19. Category: Constraints validator

Category	Constraints validator
Description	These systems facilitate the validation of RDF data by checking constraints defined in shapes.
Related activities	Data validation
Tool	Reference
ASTREA	https://astrea.linkeddata.es/
Shaclgen	https://pypi.org/project/shaclgen/
Shape designer	https://gitlab.inria.fr/jdusart/shexjapp

Table 20. Category: Triple Store / Publisher

Category	Triple Store / Publisher
Description	These systems are used to store and optionally publish RDF data. In addition, they allow for querying RDF data, in some cases the data could be stored in RDF (materialized) or the queries could be resolved in a virtualization mode from different data sources.
Related activities	Data publication
Tool	Reference
AllegroGraph	https://allegrograph.com/products/allegrograph/
GraphDB	https://graphdb.ontotext.com/
Virtuoso	https://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/
GRUFF	https://allegrograph.com/products/gruff/
IntelligentGraph	https://github.com/peterjohnlawrence/com.inova8.intelligentgraph/tree/master/olgap
Helio	https://oeg-upm.github.io/helio/
LUPOSDATE	https://github.com/luposdate/luposdate
Ontop	https://ontop-vkg.org/
RDFox	https://www.oxfordsemantic.tech/
Stardog	https://www.stardog.com/
WIMU	http://wimu.aksw.org/
YASGUI	https://github.com/TriplyDB/Yasgui

Table 21. Category: Data FAIR validator

Category	Data FAIR validator
Description	These systems assess the FAIR level of a dataset or to what extent the FAIR principles are met.
Related activities	Data publication
Tool	Reference
F-UJI	https://www.f-uji.net/

Table 22. Category: APIs

Category	APIs
Description	These systems allow for the generation and management of ontologies and data and normally are used during the generation and/or evaluation.
Related activities	Encoding, Evaluation, Data generation, Data Validation
Tool	Reference
Apache Jena	https://jena.apache.org/
OData2SPARQL	https://inova8.com/bg_inova8.com/offerings/odata2sparql/
Ontospy	http://lambdamusic.github.io/Ontospy/
OWL API	http://owlcs.github.io/owlapi/
Owlready2	https://owlready2.readthedocs.io/en/v0.35/
EMMOntoPy	https://emmo-repo.github.io/EMMO-python
Pronto	https://github.com/althonos/pronto
RDF4J	https://rdf4j.org/
RDFLib	https://rdflib.readthedocs.io/en/stable/
ROBOT	http://robot.obolibrary.org/

Table 23. Category: Project management, version management and issue tracking

Category	Project management, version management and issue tracking
Description	These tools assist ontology and knowledge graph development teams during the whole project life-cycle to manage all the generated resources and the project activities. This

	category is divided into systems for managing ontology development resources, tools for general purpose project management and communication tools.
Related activities	Whole project-life cycle
Tool	Reference
Ontology development oriented	
OnToology	http://ontology.linkeddata.es/
VocBench	https://ec.europa.eu/isa2/solutions/vocbench3_en
VoCol	https://vocol.iais.fraunhofer.de//
CENtree	https://www.scibite.com/platform/centree-ontology-management-platform/
General or software oriented	
GitHub	https://github.com/
GitLab	https://about.gitlab.com/
Jira	https://www.atlassian.com/software/jira
Mantis	https://www.mantisbt.org/
Communication tools	
Zoom	https://zoom.us/
Google Meet	https://meet.google.com/
Jitsi Meet	https://meet.jit.si/
Teams	https://www.microsoft.com/en/microsoft-teams/group-chat-software
Skype	https://www.skype.com
Webex	https://www.webex.com/
GoToMeeting	https://www.goto.com/

In order to illustrate a base scenario for building an ontology and generating a knowledge graph using such ontology, Figure 7 provides a basic workflow of activities to be carried out and potential tools to be used. It should be mentioned that all resource and project activities could be handled using tools as GitHub or other systems for sharing resources, manage tasks and track versions. In this scenario the first activity is the ontology requirements specification for which no specific tools for ontology development are used as the Ontology Requirement Specification Document can be handled in text documents (or google docs or docx) and the functional requirements are recommended to be managed with collaborative spreadsheets. It should be noted that a more detailed case could make use of THEMIS or TDDOnto to generate tests from the functional requirements.

During the ontology implementation activity, in the exemplary scenario, a first conceptualization activity is carried before looking for potential ontologies to be reused. Once there is a draft ontology model to be developed, the reuse activity makes use of specific domain registries as IndustryPortal to look for ontologies to be reused and general domain registries as LOV. Once the ontologies to be reused are selected they are incorporated into the ontology conceptualization. Before editing the ontology with an ontology editor as Protégé, developer can generate a first version of the ontology code from the ontology conceptualization diagram using Chowlk.

Then the developers should complete the ontology code according to the requirements and include metadata. After this step the ontology is evaluated, in this case OOPS! would be use to find common pitfalls and the Fact++ reasoner would be use to check potential inconsistencies. In addition, it should be checked that the ontology covers all the functional and non-functional requirements described in the Ontology Requirement Specification Document. From this activity it would be needed to go back to the encoding or conceptualization activities in case any error is found.

When the ontology is ready for publication, human readable documentation should be generated, in this case we propose Widoco to generate the HTML documentation from the OWL code. It should be noted that

the documentation generated by Widoco should be extended with examples of use of the ontology and further descriptions apart from the ones included in the ontology code. In order to publish the ontology, one could use the w3id persistent URIs and the GitHub repository for storing the files. Once the ontology is published, it could be promoted by including it in ontology repositories. In addition, when the ontology is published, ontology FAIR validator as FOOPS! Or O'FAIRE can be used to assess the ontology FAIRness level. From this point, new issues or bugs can be reported through the issue tracker system.

Once the ontology is generated it can be used to annotated data in order to generate RDF data. For doing so, during the data generation activity the existing data to be transformed into RDF could be map to the ontology concepts and properties specifying mappings using OntoRefine. This activity would generate RDF data that could be check using SHACL shapes and SHACL validators as ASTREA. If error o missing data is found during this activity, developers should go back to the data generation activity in order to improve the mappings. Finally, when the data is correct, the dataset could be stored in a triple store and made public by setting up a SPARQL endpoint, for example using GraphDB.

Figure 7. Ontology Ecosystem Reference Implementation base scenario example

5. Conclusions and future work

This document has presented the organization and final results for the 2nd focused workshop organized by WP4 focusing on ontology development and knowledge graph generation tools as well as experiences.

This deliverable also includes the ontology ecosystem reference implementation generated by aligning the ontology development and main knowledge graph generation activities to the tools identified by the tools landscape, the ones known by the partners and some mentioned by the 2nd focused workshop speaker and survey answers. In addition, a basic reference workflow for building and exploiting ontology has been provided.

A future line of work to increase the impact of the content in this deliverable is to generate an interactive and online version of the reference implementation as well as the mechanisms to keep it updated and evolve it involving communities that would be interested in maintaining such result. For example, the semantic web community as provider and user of the tools and the industry, manufacturing and related domain experts could be interested in the resource as user and providers of specific tools to be used in specific domains.

In addition, the work presented in this deliverable is planned to be extended by demonstrators feedback and use cases in order to provide a validated version of the resources in OCES that will be reported in D4.7 “Validation of methodological framework on development and documentation”. Such deliverable is intended to include as well other related resources as the recommendations for reusing Top Level, Middle level and Domain level ontologies generated as part of WP3.

6. References

- [d’Aquin et al., 2021] Mathieu d’Aquin, Alba Fernández-Izquierdo, María Poveda-Villalón, Andrew Dubber, Michela Magas, Yann Le Franc. “D4.1. Ontology ecosystem specification”. OntoCommons project deliverable. 2021.
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- [Fensel et al., 2021] Anna Fensel, Umutcan Simsek, Ana Correia, Dragan Stokic, Rebecca Sifaka, Christian Weck, Janne Haack. “D5.1 Requirements on ontology tools and ontologies and criteria for selection of further cases”. OntoCommons project deliverable. 2021.
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Annex 1

Questions from the survey to plan the 2nd focused workshop. Mandatory questions are identified with “*”.

1. With respect to ontology engineering, do you consider yourself (multiple answers possible) *
 - An expert practitioner
 - Someone who build tools to support it
 - A user of ontologies
 - Someone who would like to be more involved
 - Other:
2. With respect to Knowledge Graph (KG) and semantic data generation, do you consider yourself (multiple answers possible) *
 - An expert practitioner
 - Someone who build tools to support it
 - A user of ontologies
 - Someone who would like to be more involved
 - Other:
3. In which part(s) of the ontology engineering and KG process are you generally (would you like to be) involved? (multiple answers possible) *
 - Concept identification, ontology drafting
 - Requirement elicitation (e.g. through competency questions)
 - Identification of ontologies to reuse
 - Ontology authoring/editing
 - Ontology integration
 - Ontology testing/validation/quality assessment
 - Ontology population/instantiation
 - Ontology alignment/matching
 - Ontology modularisation
 - Ontology-based reasoning/inference
 - Ontology-based application development
 - Ontology querying/interrogation
 - Data preparation
 - Data generation
 - Data validation
 - Data exploitation

- Other:
- 4. Please list tools that you use in the OE&KG workflow. For each tool, please indicate the part(s) of the process it mostly supports (from the list above). *
 - Free text
- 5. Please list functions and features that you think are missing from those tools, or that are not sufficiently supported by those tools in your experience. *
 - Free text
- 6. Please list tools that you hear of and you would like to have more information about so that you can incorporate them in your processes. *
 - Free text

The following questions are related to the participation in the "OntoCommons OE&KG tool ecosystem Workshop". All questions are optional.

- 7. If you were attending the workshop you would prefer it to be:
 - Fully online
 - Fully presential (<https://goo.gl/maps/ELLNctbV3cBNhWyp6> UPM ETSI Informáticos, Madrid, Spain)
 - Hybrid but I won't attend
 - Hybrid and I would be physically present
- 8. If you were attending the workshop, which dates would you attend?
 - 31st August
 - 1st September
 - 2nd September
- 9. If you were attending the workshop you, which type of sessions you would like to see:
 - Toolchains presentations
 - Methodology and workflow presentations
 - Open discussions
 - Round table
 - Other:
- 10. If you wish to participate in the "OntoCommons OE&KG tool ecosystem Workshop", please provide your email address below, as a way of registering to the workshop.
 - Free text
- 11. Please indicate which level of participation you would be interested in.
 - I would like to hear from experts and participate in discussions
 - I would like to give a presentation about my experience

- I would like to be part of a panel discussing a specific topic
- I would like to either give a presentation or be part of a panel
- Other:

12. If you indicated being interested in giving a presentation and/or being part of a panel, please give us an indication of the topic to which you would want to contribute.

- Free text